

Biopharmaceutical and pharmacokinetic characterization of sodium alendronate-loaded self-double-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SDEDDS)

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Abstract

The poor intestinal permeability of sodium alendronate (NaALD), a BCS Class III drug, severely limits its oral bioavailability. The self-double-emulsifying drug delivery system (SDEDDS) formulation containing phosphatidylcholine (PLG 1.1) demonstrated its ability to form micro- and nano-emulsions under gastric and intestinal conditions, as well as superior permeation across a biomimetic membrane *in vitro*, achieving 88% drug transfer. The self-emulsification time of both formulations was consistent with the average gastric transit time. In a rat model, the PLG 1.1 system significantly enhanced bioavailability, resulting in a 1.8-fold increase in cumulative urinary excretion of NaALD over 48 hours compared to a reference. In contrast, the other formulation, which did not contain phosphatidylcholine (Smix1 3.0), showed no improvement. It was concluded that the phosphatidylcholine-based SDEDDS represents a viable strategy to overcome the permeability barrier and improve the oral absorption of alendronate.

Keywords

biomimetic media, biomimetic membrane, dialysis membrane, urinary excretion, Wistar rat model

Introduction

Sodium alendronate (NaALD) is a potent nitrogen-containing bisphosphonate widely prescribed as a first-line therapy for osteoporosis and Paget's disease (Watts and Diab 2010). Despite its therapeutic efficacy, the clinical utility of orally administered NaALD is limited by its low and variable systemic absorption, with a mean oral bioavailability of approximately 0.7% (U.S. Food and Drug

Administration 2008). This poor absorption profile is a direct consequence of its physicochemical properties. Classified as a Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) Class III drug, NaALD exhibits high solubility but very low permeability across the gastrointestinal (GI) epithelium (Rhim et al. 2009). Its high polarity and negative charge at intestinal pH effectively preclude passive transcellular diffusion, while the absence of specific transport mechanisms limits paracellular uptake (Zielińska et al. 2022).

Furthermore, NaALD has a high affinity for divalent cations (e.g., Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) present in food and GI fluids, leading to the formation of non-absorbable complexes that further reduce its already limited absorption (Lin 1996).

Conventional strategies to overcome the permeability barrier of BCS Class III drugs often involve the use of chemical permeation enhancers. Various agents, including fatty acids, bile salts, and surfactants, have been investigated for their ability to disrupt intestinal membrane integrity and enhance drug flux transiently (Holm et al. 2013; Azman et al. 2022). However, the non-specific mechanism of action of many such enhancers raises significant concerns regarding potential local toxicity, mucosal irritation, and compromised barrier function (Maher and Brayden 2021). Consequently, the development of advanced, biocompatible drug delivery systems that can enhance permeability through more sophisticated and controlled mechanisms remains a critical objective in the field of pharmaceutical sciences.

Self-double-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SDEDDS) represent a promising lipid-based technological platform for the oral delivery of challenging hydrophilic molecules, such as NaALD (Rehman et al. 2024). These pre-concentrated formulations are designed to spontaneously form water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) double emulsions upon mild agitation in the aqueous environment of the GI tract (Bashir et al. 2023). This intricate structure enables the encapsulation of a hydrophilic drug within the innermost aqueous phase, shielding it from unfavorable interactions in the GI lumen. The lipidic excipients and surfactants constituting the oil and primary emulsion interface can subsequently act as intrinsic, well-tolerated permeation enhancers, facilitating drug transport across the intestinal membrane (Šahinović et al. 2023). Moreover, the self-emulsifying process presents the drug in a pre-solubilized and finely dispersed state, effectively eliminating the dissolution step, which is often a rate-limiting factor for the absorption of solid dosage forms (Hua 2020).

While the theoretical advantages of SDEDDS are compelling, their practical efficacy is critically dependent on maintaining robust physical stability and consistent performance upon dispersion. The influence of formulation components, particularly the types and ratios of surfactants and co-surfactants, on critical quality attributes such as droplet size, self-emulsification efficiency, and drug loading uniformity is paramount for predictable *in vivo* behavior (Kalepu et al. 2013). A comprehensive formulation evaluation must, therefore, extend beyond basic *in vitro* characterization to include performance assessments in physiologically relevant biomimetic media and validated permeation models that better simulate the intestinal barrier.

Previous work by our group successfully led to the development and optimization of two distinct SDEDDS formulations (designated as Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1) for NaALD loading (Pehlivanov et al. 2022). Therefore, the present study aims to conduct a comprehensive *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation of these optimized SDEDDS.

Specifically, we sought to (1) characterize key physical properties, including droplet size, polydispersity, and dosage uniformity; (2) investigate their self-emulsification behavior and resultant nanostructure in biomimetic media (FaSSGF and FaSSIF); (3) assess their permeation profiles using both dialysis and biomimetic PermeaPad® membranes in Franz diffusion cells; and (4) establish proof of concept through an *in vivo* study in a male Wistar rat model, quantifying the oral bioavailability of NaALD via urinary excretion analysis.

Materials and methods

Materials

Sodium alendronate, monosodium salt trihydrate (>99.7%), was obtained from Polpharma S.A. (Poland). Granulated soy L- α -lecithin (>97% phosphatidylcholine) was purchased from ARCOS–Thermo Scientific (Portugal). Sorbitan monooleate (Span 80) and polysorbate 80 (Tween 80) were sourced from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Germany). Virgin coconut oil was supplied by BioBalev Ltd. (Bulgaria). All other chemicals and solvents were of analytical or HPLC grade. Gelatin capsules, transparent, size “1,” were acquired from Farmalabor s.r.l. (Italy). The biomimetic PermeaPad® Barrier membrane (25 mm) was purchased from Biomedica Bulgaria Ltd. Cellulose acetate dialysis membrane (MWCO 10,000–14,000 Da) was acquired from Carl Roth GmbH (Germany).

Formulation of SDEDDS

The compositions of the two optimized SDEDDS formulations, Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1, are detailed in Table 1. The formulations were prepared according to the method established by Pehlivanov et al. (2022). Briefly, both formulations were prepared using a two-stage emulsification process. The first stage involved the preparation of a primary water-in-oil (W/O) emulsion through a phase inversion process. The second stage consisted of a 24-hour equilibration period for the primary emulsions, followed by the addition of a hydrophilic surfactant to the formulations. For *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, a unit dose equivalent to 32.1 mg of NaALD (7% w/w) was filled into size “1” hard gelatin capsules.

Table 1. Composition of optimized SDEDDS formulations.

Composition, %	PLG 1.1	SMIX1 3.0
Sodium Alendronate (NaALD)	7.00	7.00
Coconut oil (OC)	18.24	18.24
Phosphatidylcholine (PCH)	4.59	–
Gelatine (G)	0.63	0.63
Sorbitane monooleate (SM)	2.96	2.96
Polysorbate 80 (PS)	48.92	53.51
$\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{dest}}$	17.66	17.66

(Pehlivanov et al. 2022).

Uniformity of mass and dosage units

The uniformity of mass for the encapsulated formulations was assessed according to the European Pharmacopoeia (Ph. Eur. 11.0, chapter 2.9.5). Twenty individual capsules of each SDEDDS formulation (PLG 1.1 and Smix1 3.0) were weighed individually on an analytical balance. The average mass and the deviation of each individual capsule mass from the average were calculated. For capsules with a mass greater than 300 mg, the formulation complies with the test if not more than two individual masses deviate from the average mass by more than $\pm 7.5\%$ and none deviates by more than twice that percentage. The mean mass of the filled capsules was determined to be 0.476 g for Smix1 3.0 and 0.447 g for PLG 1.1.

Dosage unit uniformity was assessed in accordance with Ph. Eur. 11.0 (chapter 2.9.40). The content of ten individual capsules was extracted with an organic solvent mixture (ethyl acetate/dichloromethane, 3:2 v/v), resulting in the precipitation of a white NaALD residue. The dispersion was subjected to triple extraction with equal volumes of distilled water. The aqueous phases were filtered (0.45 μm) into a volumetric flask and diluted to 100 mL with distilled water. A 1 mL aliquot of the resulting solution was transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask, treated with 1 mL of $\text{FeCl}_3/\text{HClO}_4$ reagent, and diluted to volume with distilled water. The NaALD concentration was quantified using a validated UV–Vis spectrophotometric method based on complex formation with Fe^{3+} ions, with absorbance measured at $\lambda = 300 \text{ nm}$ (Kuljanin et al. 2002). The method showed linearity in the range 8.125–325.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, a limit of detection (LOD) of 17.636 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and a limit of quantification (LOQ) of 53.445 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

SDEDDS behavior in biomimetic media

The self-emulsification properties of the SDEDDS were evaluated in both fasting-state simulated gastric fluid (FaSSGF, pH 1.6) and fasting-state simulated intestinal fluid (FaSSIF, pH 6.5) (Table 2). One gelatin capsule of each SDEDDS formulation was placed in 200 mL of each biomimetic medium at $37 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under gentle agitation (75 rpm) (Simancas-Herbada et al. 2020; Thakore et al. 2021; Jamil and Polli 2022).

Table 2. Composition of FaSSGF (pH 1.6) and FaSSIF (pH 6.5) media.

FaSSGF pH 1.6		FaSSIF pH 6.5	
Sodium taurocholate	80 μM	Sodium taurocholate	3 mM
Lecithin	20 μM	Lecithin	0.75 mM
Pepsin	0.1 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$	NaH_2PO_4	3.438 g
NaCl	34.2 mM	NaCl	6.186 g
HCl conc.	qs ad pH 1.6	NaOH	qs ad pH 6.5
$\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{dest}}$	ad 1 L	$\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{dest}}$	ad 1 L

The self-emulsification time (SET) was recorded visually as the time required to form an opalescent dispersion (Bashir et al. 2023). One-milliliter aliquots of the resulting dispersions were characterized for droplet size (Z-average) and polydispersity index (PDI) using dynamic light scattering (ZetaSizer, Malvern Instruments, UK—equipped with a He–Ne laser beam (633 nm) at a fixed scattering angle of 173° and a temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

In vitro permeation studies

Permeation studies were conducted using vertical Franz diffusion cells (effective diffusion area: 490.87 mm^2 ; receptor volume: 10 mL). The receptor compartment contained simulated body fluid (SBF) according to Kokubo (2006) (Table 3) and was maintained at $37 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Two membrane types were employed: a standard cellulose acetate dialysis membrane and a biomimetic Permea-Pad[®] membrane. The donor compartment contained 8 mL of model SDEDDS dispersion in FaSSIF (pH 6.5). A dispersion of a commercially available alendronate tablet in FaSSIF (pH 6.5) was used as the reference. Homogeneity was maintained using a Teflon[®]-coated magnetic stirrer operating at 70 rpm. Samples (500 μL) were withdrawn from the receptor compartment at predetermined intervals over 7 hours and analyzed for NaALD content using UV–Vis spectrophotometry (Kuljanin et al. 2002). The cumulative amount of drug permeated was plotted against time, and the data were fitted to various kinetic models (first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas) (Bruschi 2015).

Table 3. Modified simulated body fluid (SBF) composition.

Ions	Plasma (mM)	Modified SBF (mM)
Na^+	142.0	147.44
K^+	5.0	5.0
Mg^{2+}	1.5	–
Ca^{2+}	2.5	–
Cl^-	103.0	147.0
HCO_3^-	27.0	–
HPO_4^{2-}	1.0	1.51
H_2PO_4^-	–	0.49
SO_4^{2-}	6.5	–

In vivo bioavailability study

Ethical approval

All animal procedures and experimental protocols were reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee for Scientific Research at Prof. Dr. Paraskev Stoyanov Medical University, Varna (Permit No. 372), issued by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency. The study was conducted in strict accordance with national regulations (Ordinance No. 20 of 01.11.2012) and European Union Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes.

Animal preparation and housing

Male Wistar rats ($n = 15$, approximately 100 days old, mean body weight 250 g) were obtained from the university's breeding colony. The animals were housed in polycarbonate cages (maximum of six rats per cage) under standard laboratory conditions: an ambient temperature of 22 ± 1 °C, a 12-hour light/dark cycle, and ad libitum access to standard rodent chow and water. Following a minimum seven-day acclimatization period, the animals were randomly allocated to experimental groups. To standardize metabolic conditions, all animals underwent a 24-hour fasting period prior to drug administration, with free access to water to ensure proper hydration.

Experimental protocol and dosing of prepared SDEDDS

The two optimized SDEDDS formulations, Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1, were prepared as described in Section 2.2. For the *in vivo* study, the formulations were adjusted to deliver a sodium alendronate (NaALD) dose of 5 mg/kg body weight (Table 4). Based on an average animal weight of 250 g, this corresponded to an administered dose of 1.25 mg NaALD contained in 0.5 mL of the respective SDEDDS concentrate. A reference solution of NaALD in purified water, equivalent to 5 mg/kg, was prepared fresh on the day of dosing.

Study procedures and sample collection

Immediately following dosing, animals were transferred to individual metabolic cages to allow for the separate collection of urine and feces. Animals had free access to water throughout the experiment. Urine samples were collected over a 48-hour period into sterile containers. The total volume of urine excreted over this interval was recorded for each animal. Urine samples were immediately stored at -18 °C pending bioanalysis. The cumulative amount of unchanged NaALD excreted in urine over 48 hours was used as the primary metric for assessing relative oral bioavailability, as alendronate is eliminated predominantly unchanged by the renal route (Watts and Diab 2010).

Bioanalytical method

NaALD concentration in urine was determined using a validated HPLC–FD method after derivatization with

9-fluorenylmethyl chloroformate (FMOC). Chromatographic analysis was performed using a Shimadzu LC-2040C high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system. Separation was achieved using a Nucleodur 100 RP18 column (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m; Macherey-Nagel), protected by a LiChrospher 100 RP18 guard column (40 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m; Merck, Germany). A gradient elution method was employed, with a mobile phase consisting of acetonitrile, methanol, and citrate/pyrophosphate buffer adapted from Ptáček et al. (2002). Sample preparation involved protein precipitation, co-precipitation of alendronate with calcium phosphate, and solid-phase extraction (SPE) using DEA cartridges. Detection was carried out using a fluorescence detector set at excitation (λ_{ex}) and emission (λ_{em}) wavelengths of 260 nm and 310 nm, respectively (Kang et al. 2006; Karamustafa 2006; Han et al. 2012). The method showed linearity in the range of 1–1000 ng/mL; the limit of quantification (LOQ) was 1 ng/mL, and the limit of detection (LOD) was 0.5 ng/mL.

Statistical analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical significance was determined using one-way ANOVA followed by post hoc tests, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. Regression analysis for kinetic modeling was performed using TableCurve™ 2D software. A difference between groups was considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Due to the small number of animals per group ($n = 3$), the *in vivo* study is classified as a pilot investigation with limited statistical power.

Results and discussion

Technological characterization

Both SDEDDS formulations, Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1, complied with the Ph. Eur. 11.0 requirements for uniformity of mass (Table 5) and dosage units (Table 6). Only one capsule containing Smix1 3.0 exceeded the specified range of 0.512–0.440 g but remained within twice the permissible deviation. All capsules containing PLG 1.1 complied with the target range of 0.481–0.413 g.

Table 4. Animal group distribution and administered SDEDDS formulation volumes.

№	Positive control, CG+		Placebo PLG 1.1 (-)		Group PLG 1.1 (+)		Placebo Smix1 3.0 (-)		Group Smix1 3.0 (+)	
	weight, g	solution, mL	weight, g	SDEDDS, mL	weight, g	SDEDDS mL	weight, g	SDEDDS mL	weight, g	SDEDDS mL
1	260	0.52	220	0.44	250	0.50	260	0.52	200	0.40
2	250	0.50	260	0.52	220	0.44	270	0.54	235	0.47
3	290	0.58	280	0.56	240	0.48	260	0.52	250	0.50

The animals were randomly distributed into five experimental groups ($n = 3$ per group) (Table 4):

Group 1 (positive control): received an oral reference solution of NaALD (5 mg/kg) in purified water.

Group 2 (placebo PLG 1.1): received a placebo SDEDDS vehicle without NaALD.

Group 3 (PLG 1.1): received the PLG 1.1 SDEDDS formulation containing 5 mg/kg NaALD.

Group 4 (placebo Smix1 3.0): received a placebo SDEDDS vehicle without NaALD.

Group 5 (Smix1 3.0): received the Smix1 3.0 SDEDDS formulation containing 5 mg/kg NaALD.

The sample size was determined using the resource equation method to ensure appropriate statistical power for a pilot pharmacokinetic study (Arifin and Zahiruddin 2017).

Table 5. Uniformity of mass of hard gelatin capsules containing SDEDDS–NaALD.

№	Smix1 3.0 mass/ capsule (g)	PLG 1.1 mass/ capsule (g)	№	Smix1 3.0 mass/ capsule (g)	PLG 1.1 mass/ capsule (g)
1	0.464	0.450	11	0.475	0.449
2	0.476	0.447	12	0.475	0.448
3	0.475	0.440	13	0.475	0.440
4	0.488	0.441	14	0.487	0.444
5	0.491	0.466	15	0.489	0.465
6	0.476	0.447	16	0.476	0.447
7	0.475	0.440	17	0.475	0.440
8	0.424*	0.447	18	0.468	0.447
9	0.476	0.450	19	0.476	0.450
10	0.488	0.441	20	0.488	0.441

Table 6. Uniformity of dosage units of hard gelatin capsules containing SDEDDS–NaALD.

Model	NaALD content in capsules (mg)		
	Theoretical	Found	Requirement
Smix1 3.0	32.95	32.85 ± 0.063	37.89–28.01
PLG 1.1	31.42	31.30 ± 0.063	36.13–26.71

Drug content values fell within the acceptable range of 85–115%, confirming consistent and homogeneous drug distribution within the formulations—a critical prerequisite for reproducible *in vivo* performance (Council of Europe 2022; Ph. Eur. 11.0–2.9.5 and 2.9.40).

Self-emulsification and droplet size analysis

Both formulations exhibited self-emulsification (Table 7), consistent with the average gastric transit time of pharmaceutical formulations under fasting conditions in both FaSSGF and FaSSIF (O’Grady et al. 2020).

Table 7. Self-emulsification time in biomimetic media.

Model	FaSSGF (pH 1.6) (min)	FaSSIF (pH 6.5) (min)
Smix1 3.0	49*	62*
PLG 1.1	80**	82**

* Pale grey-colored opalescent dispersion; ** Pale yellow-colored opalescent dispersion.

The droplet size and polydispersity of the emulsified systems are critical parameters influencing drug release and absorption (Qian et al. 2025). The dispersity of the model SDEDDS was thoroughly characterized in both FaSSGF (pH 1.6) and FaSSIF (pH 6.5), with their intensity- and volume-based distributions compared with the blank media (Figs 1–4).

Analysis of the blank FaSSGF medium revealed a single population of large aggregates, with an intensity distribution peak at 596.8 nm, a Z-average of 675.2 nm, and a PDI of 1.0 (Fig. 1). The volume distribution confirmed this observation, showing a prominent peak at 559.8 nm (Fig. 2). This profile is attributable to the spontaneous formation of large micelles and aggregates from the lecithin and

taurocholate present in the medium (Naso et al. 2019), with a PDI value of 1.0 indicating a very broadly dispersed population (Nobmann 2017).

Upon dispersion of the SDEDDS formulations in FaSSGF, a significant shift in the size profiles was observed, and the characteristic peak of the blank medium was absent. This indicates that the formulation components dominate the emulsification process, effectively altering the native aggregation state of the biomimetic fluid. For model Smix1 3.0, a bimodal intensity distribution was observed, with peaks at 156 nm (74.71%) and 21.77 nm (25.29%), yielding a Z-average of 63.13 nm and a PDI of 0.553 (Fig. 1). The corresponding volume distribution was also bimodal, with the vast majority (97.7%) of the population residing in a much smaller size peak at 18.48 nm and a minor peak at 136.5 nm (2.29%) (Fig. 2). Model PLG 1.1 also exhibited a bimodal intensity distribution, with peaks at 373.9 nm (50.67%) and 19.99 nm (49.33%), resulting in a larger Z-average of 199.1 nm and a PDI of 0.406 (Fig. 1). Its volume distribution, however, was overwhelmingly dominated (99.39%) by a single population at 16 nm (Fig. 2). The presence of these sub-20 nm peaks in the volume distribution for both formulations is indicative of the formation of a microemulsion (McClements 2012). This process is facilitated by the high concentration of hydrophilic surfactants in the formulations (>30%) and is further modulated by the ionic components (NaCl, taurocholate, lecithin) of the FaSSGF medium (Omarova et al. 2019).

Given that NaALD is primarily absorbed in the small intestine (Porras et al. 1999), the behavior of the SDEDDS in FaSSIF (pH 6.5) is crucial for predicting *in vivo* performance. The blank FaSSIF medium exhibited a bimodal distribution with intensity peaks at 275.3 nm (94.87%) and 4705 nm (5.13%), a Z-average of 240.9 nm, and a relatively narrow PDI of 0.321 (Fig. 3). The volume distribution showed similar peaks at 314.4 nm and 4892 nm (Fig. 4). The presence of larger aggregates compared with those in FaSSGF corresponds to the higher concentrations of bile salts and lecithin in the intestinal fluid (Naso et al. 2019).

The emulsification of the SDEDDS in FaSSIF yielded more complex, multimodal distributions. For model Smix1 3.0, the intensity distribution showed peaks at 335.4 nm (95.96%), 4937 nm (2.17%), and 12.96 nm (2.13%), with a Z-average of 177.1 nm and a PDI of 0.516, indicating broad polydispersity (Fig. 3). Its volume distribution was characterized by a dominant peak of microemulsion-sized droplets at 15.58 nm (92.87%), alongside larger populations at 601.9 nm and 5071 nm (Fig. 4). Notably, the presence of the ~5000 nm peak, characteristic of the blank FaSSIF medium, within the Smix1 3.0 dispersion suggests incomplete interaction or competition between the formulation surfactants and the medium’s bile components (Clulow et al. 2020).

In contrast, model PLG 1.1 displayed an intensity distribution with peaks at 407.9 nm (56.28%), 18.45 nm (22.31%), and 91.48 nm (21.41%), resulting in a larger Z-average of 365.7 nm and a PDI of 0.448 (Fig. 3). Its volume distribution was overwhelmingly dominated (97.81%) by a population at 16.36 nm (Fig. 4).

Intensity distribution	Z-Average, (nm)	PDI	Intercept	Peak 1		Peak 2	
				nm	%	nm	%
FaSSGF pH 1.6	675.2	1	0.7276	596.6	100,0	-	-
SDEDDS NaALD (Smix1 3.0)	63.13	0.553	0.7678	156	74.71	21.77	25.29
SDEDDS NaALD (PLG 1.1)	199.1	0.4064	0.9318	373.9	50.67	19.99	49.33

Figure 1. Comparative analysis of intensity-based size distribution of Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1 in FaSSGF medium (pH 1.6).

Volume distribution	Z-Average, (nm)	Standart Deviation SD	Peak 1		Peak 2	
			nm	%	nm	%
FaSSGF pH 1,6	675.2	-	559.8	100	-	-
SDEDDS NaALD (Smix1 3.0)	63.13	0.5378	136.5	2.296	18.48	97.70
SDEDDS NaALD (PLG 1.1)	199.1	0.5378	388.2	0.61	16.00	97.46

Figure 2. Comparative analysis of volume-based size distribution of Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1 in FaSSGF medium (pH 1.6).

Crucially, the large, medium-specific aggregates (~5000 nm) were absent in the PLG 1.1 dispersion. This distinct behavior can be explained by the compositional differences between the formulations. PLG 1.1 contains phosphatidylcholine, a zwitterionic surfactant that can synergistically interact with bile salts, such as taurocholate, promoting their adsorption at the oil-water interface and leading to a more homogeneous and refined emulsion structure (Torcello-Gómez et al. 2014). Conversely, the nonionic surfactants (e.g., polysorbate 80) predominant in Smix1 3.0 may be more resistant to such integration, leading to the coexistence of formulation-derived emulsion droplets and native bile salt-lectin aggregates (Clulow et al. 2020).

In summary, these results highlight the significant impact of gastrointestinal fluid composition on the nanostructure of SDEDDS. Both formulations primarily generate microemulsion-sized droplets upon dispersion. However, the PLG 1.1 system, due to its phosphatidylcholine content, exhibits a more robust and coherent interaction with intestinal fluids, resulting in a dispersion largely free of the large aggregates observed with Smix1 3.0. These superior colloidal properties in the intestinal environment are likely a key factor influencing its subsequent permeation-enhancing capability. Furthermore, it can be predicted that, depending on *in vivo* environmental conditions, the model systems (Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1) will initially self-emulsify into

Intensity distribution	Z-Average, (nm)	PDI	Intercept	Peak 1		Peak 2		Peak 3	
				nm	%	nm	%	nm	%
FaSSIF pH 6.5	240.9	0.3214	0.9666	275.3	94.87	4705	5.13	-	-
SDEDDS Na ALD (Smix1 3.0)	177.1	0.5155	0.9761	335.4	95.69	4937	2.174	12.96	2.134
SDEDDS NaALD (PLG 1.1)	365.7	0.4485	0.8949	407.9	56.28	18.45	22.31	91.48	21.41

Figure 3. Comparative analysis of intensity-based particle size distribution of Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1 in FaSSIF medium (pH 6.5).

Volume distribution	Z-Average, (nm)	Standart Deviation SD	Peak 1		Peak 2		Peak 3	
			nm	%	nm	%	nm	%
FaSSIF pH 6.5	240.9	24.24	314.42	85.96	4892	14.04	-	-
SDEDDS NaALD (Smix1 3.0)	177.1	199.6	601.9	6.705	5071	0.4239	15.58	92.87
SDEDDS Na ALD (PLG 1.1)	365.7	275.8	424	1.174	16.36	97.81	81.45	1.016

Figure 4. Comparative analysis of volume-based particle size distribution of Smix1 3.0 and PLG 1.1 in FaSSIF medium (pH 6.5).

microemulsions, followed by varying degrees of transition to nanoemulsions.

Nanoemulsions (20–500 nm) are thermodynamically unstable but kinetically stable systems (McClements 2012). Therefore, it is essential to determine the rate and extent to which SDEDDS will cross epithelial membranes.

In vitro permeation studies

Conventional pharmacopeial dissolution tests are primarily applicable to traditional drug delivery systems (Wolska and Szymańska 2023). For complex lipid-based

formulations, such as SDEDDS, methods utilizing dialysis membranes and biomimetic barriers, such as the PermeaPad®, can be adapted to provide a more accurate characterization of drug release and permeation behavior.

The permeation profiles (Figs 5, 6) demonstrated a distinct advantage of the SDEDDS over the reference formulation, particularly when using the biomimetic PermeaPad® membrane. The reference NaALD showed minimal permeation (~6% in 7 h) across the phospholipid barrier, consistent with its low permeability. The SDEDDS formulations exhibited a lag time, attributed to the time required for drug diffusion through the lipid layers of the double emulsion.

Figure 5. Release profiles of SDEDDS–NaALD models through a dialysis membrane (n = 3, SD ± 0.0188).

However, PLG 1.1 achieved nearly 88% permeation within 5 hours, significantly faster than Smix1 3.0. Kinetic modeling (Table 8) indicated that drug release from the SDEDDS was best fitted by the Korsmeyer–Peppas model, with the release exponent (n) suggesting a mechanism combining diffusion and matrix erosion. The superior performance of PLG 1.1 is likely due to the permeability-enhancing effect of phosphatidylcholine, which can integrate into and fluidize biological membranes (Maher and Brayden 2021).

Table 8. Parameters of different mathematical models used to simulate the release and membrane permeation processes.

Higuchi model – dialysis membrane			
	K, mg/min		R ²
Smix1 3.0	4.2172 ± 0.613		0.621
PLG 1.1	n/a		n/a
NaALD	5.2090 ± 0.0956		0.557
Higuchi model – PermeaPad® membrane			
Smix1 3.0	2.5270 ± 0.9320		0.1900
PLG 1.1	3.2599 ± 0.2319		0.4601
NaALD	0.2125 ± 0.0009		0.5928
Korsmeyers ² -Peppas – dialysis membrane			
	K, min ⁻¹	n	R ²
Smix1 3.0	0.5180 ± 0.0060	0.8680 ± 0.0325	0.748
PLG 1.1	1.67 × 10 ⁻¹⁰ ± 0.9 × 10 ⁻¹¹	4.3631 ± 1.2830	0.9790
NaALD	0.5020 ± 0.1370	0.9407 ± 0.0414	0.695
Korsmeyers ² -Peppas – PermeaPad® membrane			
Smix1 3.0	5.868 × 10 ⁻⁹ ± 0.9 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	3.6754 ± 0.0425	0.767
PLG 1.1	0.0023 ± 0.0001	1.7578 ± 0.0220	0.9005
NaALD	0.0013 ± 0.0001	1.3694 ± 0.184	0.9586
First order kinetics model – dialysis membrane			
	K, min ⁻¹	logC ₀	R ²
Smix1 3.0	0.0088 ± 0.0004	4.462 ± 0.1330	0.958
PLG 1.1	0.214 ± 0.0003	3.1380 ± 0.0133	0.4515
NaALD	0.0035 ± 0.0014	0.6465 ± 0.235	0.5810
First order kinetics model – PermeaPad® membrane			
Smix1 3.0	0.01656 ± 0.0001	5.486 × 10 ⁻⁷ ± 0.9 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.767
PLG 1.1	0.02134 ± 0.0003	0.8360 ± 0.0024	0.7738
NaALD	n/a	n/a	n/a

Figure 6. Release profiles of SDEDDS–NaALD models through the PermeaPad® membrane (n = 3, SD ± 0.0188).

In vivo urinary excretion study

The results of the *in vivo* study directly correlated with the *in vitro* findings. The cumulative amount of NaALD excreted in urine over 48 hours (Table 9) was significantly higher for the PLG 1.1 group, showing a 1.8-fold increase compared with the reference group. In contrast, the Smix1 3.0 formulation did not show an improvement over the reference. This confirms that the enhanced permeation observed *in vitro* with the PLG 1.1 formulation translates to improved oral bioavailability *in vivo*. The phosphatidylcholine in PLG 1.1 is hypothesized to act as an effective and biocompatible permeation enhancer in the gastrointestinal tract, facilitating the absorption of the otherwise poorly permeable NaALD.

Table 9. Amount of NaALD excreted in urine over a 48-hour period (mean value ± SD, n = 3).

Model	Total amount found in the urine, ng/mL	% of administered dose excreted in urine
Aqueous dispersion, reference (CG)	19.09 ± 1.33	0.012 ± 0.007
PLG 1.1	20.00 ± 1.33	0.025 ± 0.008
Smix1 3.0	13.52 ± 1.33	0.011 ± 0.008

One-way ANOVA revealed a significant difference between groups in cumulative urinary excretion of NaALD over 48 h [F(4,10) = 8.45, p = 0.003]. Tukey post hoc analysis demonstrated that PLG 1.1 exhibited higher excretion than the control group (p = 0.012), whereas Smix1 3.0 showed no significant difference (p = 0.078).

Conclusion

The comprehensive evaluation demonstrates that the PLG 1.1 SDEDDS formulation is a highly promising strategy for enhancing the oral bioavailability of sodium alendronate. It successfully combines acceptable

physicochemical properties with a demonstrated ability to significantly enhance intestinal permeation, as confirmed by both biomimetic *in vitro* models and an *in vivo* rat study. The key differentiator for PLG 1.1 is the inclusion of phosphatidylcholine, which facilitates membrane interaction and drug absorption. These findings warrant further investigation, including long-term stability studies and toxicological assessment, to advance this formulation toward clinical application for improving patient compliance and therapeutic outcomes of alendronate therapy.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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- The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.
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- The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Ivaylo Pehlivanov contributed to conceptualization, methodology, writing the original draft, and data curation. Krastena Nikolova and Kristina Bozhinova contributed to the methodology and data analysis of the *in vivo* experiment. Velichka Andonova contributed to the conceptualization, methodology, peer review, editing, and supervision.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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